

On Activated Charcoal. Part II. Purification by Washing with Water and by Activation.

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It has been reported by Roychoudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 433) and Roychoudhury and Mukherjee (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 157, 435) that the negative charge of the sugar charcoal diminishes on repeated washing with pure water and ultimately becomes positive on further activation. The conclusion was drawn that the primarily adsorbed layer of ions on the surface of charcoal determines its property, such as, the adsorption of acids or alkalis and the liberation of alkali or acid by neutral salt solution.

Kolthoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4473) found that charcoal activated at 900—1000° and heated, thereafter, in oxygen at 300°-500° forms on its surface a definite chemical compound with an acid character. The optimum temperature for preparing this acid charcoal is 400°. He also found that a suspension of C₄₀₀° in water was negatively charged while a similar suspension of C₉₅₀° in water was positively charged. Also, if C₉₅₀° be shaken with an inorganic salt solution, hydrolytic adsorption of the acid takes place and the filtrate has an alkaline reaction. If on the other hand, C₄₈₀° be shaken with an inorganic salt solution, the filtrate has an acid reaction. These observations are in agreement with those of Roychoudhury and Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*).

Miller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2967) objects to the procedure employed by Roychoudhury (*loc. cit.*) for heating the charcoal for activation at 600°, which, according to Miller, is not high enough to drive off the acid products on the charcoal surface. But Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) states "by heating C₄₀₀° for 24 hours in a vacuum at 620° it assumes the properties of C₉₅₀°. The acid has been removed from the surface and it adsorbs inorganic and organic acids almost to the same extent as C₅₀₀°."

Miller (*loc. cit.*) also states that the washing with boiling pure water followed by activation is not sufficient for the purification, as

quantities of acids can be irreversibly adsorbed on the charcoal leaving no detectable amount of acid in solution.

Miller, however, finds that "at boiling temperature there was an appreciable quantity of acid extracted in solution." Roychoudhury (*loc. cit.*) had, however, decanted off the hot supernatant liquid and determined its specific conductivity, when it was sufficiently cold and the supernatant liquid was not allowed to become cold in contact with the charcoal.

It seems that Miller's objections to the procedures are based on misconceptions. Further, the object of the work of Roychoudhury and Mukherjee was to investigate the relationship between the surface charge and the adsorption of acids and bases or their liberation with neutral salts, and the charcoals with acidic surface layers were of as much interest as those without it.

Ockrent (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 301) holds that the oxide theory of the composition of the surface layer of activated charcoal is fallacious and that the differences in the adsorptive properties of charcoal, activated at different temperatures, are associated with the existence or absence of the high temperature adsorbed water layer. If the contentions of Ockrent be correct then the arrangement of Miller in removing surface oxides appears to be invalidated.

Further experiments have been carried out to ascertain the extent of purification which can be effected by the same procedure (Roychoudhury, *loc. cit.*). The samples of charcoals were also prepared in the same way.

RESULTS.

Effect of Washing and Activation.

Table I shows the results of washing directly after ignition of a sample of negative charcoal (A). 50 G. of charcoal were boiled with a litre of conductivity water for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. Different stages of washing and activation at which the negative charge of sample A becomes zero have been indicated in the table by A₁, A₂ and A₃. The electro-osmotic movement of the bubble is given in cm. per 3 minutes at 36°-38° (Roychoudhury, *loc. cit.*), the proportion of charcoal and

water being the same as used in the washing and the time of contact of charcoal and water being either 2 hours or 24 hours as indicated below.

TABLE I.

Sample.	No. of washings ($1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. boiling).	Sp. conductivity of water used $\times 10^6$ (35°).	Sp. conductivity of supernat. liquid $\times 10^6$ (35°).	Rate of elec- tro-osmosis (contact for 2 hrs).
A	1	2.2	6.8	
	2	"	4.4	
	3	"	4.6	
	4	"	2.9	
	5	1.7	2.2	
	6	2.2	2.9	
	7	"	2.7	-24.1
	8	1.7	2.4	
	9	1.9	1.9	-15.1
	10	1.4	2.2	
	11	2.2	2.0	
A ₁ (activated for 6 hours at 800°)	12	1.7	2.0	0*
	13	1.4	4.4	
	14	"	3.7	
	15	"	3.1	
A ₂ (activated for 6 hours at 800°)	16	1.7	2.2	0*
	17	1.4	6.3	
	18	2.2	5.5	
	19	"	4.9	
A ₃ (activated for 6 hours at 800°)	20	"	4.4	0*

Table II gives the results for another sample, B. At the third washing the charge was measured and the electro-osmotic movement of the bubble was found to be -11.0 cm. in 3 minutes. After the 13th washing the charcoal was activated (B_1), which was activated without further boiling with water (B_2). This process of activation without boiling with water was continued until B_4 was obtained.

* No variation of charge even after 24 hours' contact.

TABLE II.

Sample.	No. of washings (15 min. boiling, 250 c.c. water + 50 g. of char- coal).	Specific conductivity of water used $\times 10^6$ (35°).	Specific conductivity of supernat. liquid $\times 10^6$ (35°).	Rate of elec- tro-osmosis (contact for 2 hours).
B	1	2.0	8.0	
	2	"	7.0	
	3	"	8.0	-11.0
	4	"	6.5	
	5	"	6.0	
	6	"	6.5	
	7	"	5.0	
	8	"	3.8	
	9	"	3.9	
	10	"	3.7	
	11	"	3.7	
	12	"	2.5	
B ₁ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	13	"	3.6	-11.3
B ₂ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	...	...	...	-0.2
B ₃ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	...	...	...	0
B ₄ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	...	...	...	0

It will be seen that the procedure of purification always leads to the promotion of charcoal with a discharged surface (iso-electric or null charcoal) and that on activation electrolytes are liberated from the surface which increases the specific conductivity of the washing water.

A portion of A was next treated with concentrated HCl before washing with conductivity water. The resulting charcoal C was then treated in a similar manner. The data are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Sample.	Boiled for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hrs. + 50 g. charcoal.	Specific conductivity of water used $\times 10^6$ (35°).	Specific conductivity of supernat. liquid $\times 10^6$ (35°).	Rate of electro-osmosis.
C	1	1.9	7.4	-13
	2	2.2	4.9	
	3	"	21	
	4	"	"	-27.4
	5	1.4	22	
	6	2.9	"	
	7	"	24	
	8	"	22	
	9	"	19	
	10	"	"	
	11	2.2	14.8	
C ₁ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	12	2.3	"	-2.9
	13	1.2	185	
	14	1.5	66	
	15	1.4	44	
	16	"	"	
	17	2.1	29	
	18	1.7	24	
	19	2.2	20	
	20	1.4	"	
	C ₂ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	21	"	
22		2.2	22	
23		"	21	
24		1.4	22	
25		"	17	
26		"	"	
27		2.2	21	
28		"	19	
29		1.7	17	
C ₃ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	30	"	"	0
	31	"	22	
	32	"	21	
	33	"	17	
	34	"	"	
	35	1.4	15	
C ₄ (activated for 6 hrs. at 800°)	36	"	"	0

Apparently it is difficult to remove the last traces of hydrochloric acid and activation was not sufficient to remove the last traces of the acid at the pressure of 10 mm. at which the activation was carried out, though the surface has already become neutral after the activation.

The surface charge of various samples of activated charcoal in contact with water is given in Table IV. The time of contact of the charcoal with water was 2 hours in each case. For the sake of comparison, some of them were also left in contact with the water inside the endosmotic tube for 24 hours. A₄ has been obtained after activating A₃ for 6 hours at 550°. B₅ was obtained from B₄ after activation at 550° in a new silica tube and B₆ was obtained from B₅ on further activation. D₁ is an unactivated coarse negatively charged sugar charcoal which on activation at 550° for 8 hours gave D₂; E is a sample of sugar charcoal positively charged; F₁ is also a sample of sugar charcoal not washed before activation and on first activation gave F₂, which on further activation gave F₃.

TABLE IV.

Activated sample.	No. of washings.	Temp. of activation.	Time of heating.	Rates of electro-osmosis.
A ₁	20	800°	6 hrs.	0
A ₂	...	"	"	0
A ₃	...	"	"	0
A ₄	...	550°	"	0
B ₁	...	800°	"	-11.3
B ₂	...	"	8	-0.2
B ₃	...	850°	"	0
B ₄	...	"	6	0
B ₅	...	550°	"	0
B ₆	...	850°	"	0
C ₁	12	800°	6 hrs.	-2.9
C ₂	...	"	"	-3.0
C ₃	30	"	"	0
C ₄	36	"	"	0
D ₁	...	550°	8	-1.4
D ₂	...	575° (in a new silica tube)	6	+0.8
E	...	550°	"	+2.1
F ₁	Not washed	"	"	-2.6
F ₂	...	"	"	0
F ₃	...	"	"	0

The negative charge invariably diminishes by continual washing and activation until the zero is reached. The negative charcoal could, however, be transformed into positive charcoal only in two instances (D_2 and I). In the case of D_2 the positive charge became zero after keeping the charcoal and water in contact for 24 hours. By the same treatment the positive charge of I decreased from 2.1 to 0.8 cm.

There is thus a general tendency for the specific conductivity of the supernatant liquid of charcoal to be decreased on successive washings which indicates that surface impurities are being gradually removed by this treatment. The fact that the negative charge of impure charcoal gradually decreases and becomes zero and then becomes positive shows that the removal of surface impurities plays a very important rôle in determining the surface charge of the charcoal. The positive charge in contact with pure water appears to be the best index of the purity of a charcoal surface. The difficulty in getting a positively charged surface lies in the removal of the last traces of electrolytic impurities. This explains why positively charged charcoals are not always produced under the conditions studied. Simply boiling the charcoal with conductivity water does not help much to decrease the negative charge unless the process of boiling is assisted by activation.

It has been contended by Miller that it is doubtful if all the acidic impurities can be removed by heating at 600° . It will be observed that positive charcoal can be obtained by heating the charcoal between 550° to 600° (D_2 and I).

Effect of Electrolytes on the Surface Charge.

The measurements were carried out at room temperature (27° - 28°), 250 C.c. of the electrolytic solution were shaken with 15 g. of the charcoal. The time of contact was 24 hours.

TABLE V.

Sample A (negative).

Conc.	Movement of bubble in cm. per 3 minutes			
	HCl.	H ₂ SO ₄	NaOH.	NaCl.
0	-12.05	-8.95	-9.8	-8.5
0.0001N	-11.65	-9.2	-13.9	-11.7
0.0002	-10.1	--	-18.1	-17.2

TABLE VI.

Sample A₃ (iso-electric).

Conc.	Movement of bubble in cm. per 3 minutes.	
	HCl.	H ₂ SO ₄ .
0	0	0
0·0001 N	-3·9	-6·8
0·0002	-7·0	-17·0
0·0004	-12·3	—
0·0005	-10·4	—

TABLE VII.

Sample D (positive).

Electro-osmotic experiments with positively charged sugar charcoal (vide Table VI).

Conc.	Movement of the bubble in cm. per 3 minutes.
	HCl
0	+0·8
0·0001 N	0
0·0002	0
0·001	+4·0

For comparison the following data from Roychoudury (*loc. cit.*) is given.

TABLE VIII.

Experiments with positively charged sugar charcoal with the addition of electrolytes (From Roychoudhury, J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1931, 8, 560).

Conc.	HCl.		H ₂ SO ₄ .	NaOH.
	Sample I.	Sample II.		
0	1·5	+1·3	+6·13	+0·9
0·0001 N	-0·25	-0·35	-0·1	-0·25
0·0002	-0·25	-0·4	-0·45	-0·45
0·001	+1·0	+0·78	-3·0	-0·91

S U M M A R Y.

1. It appears that the charge of positively charged charcoal is least affected by the above electrolytes. It is difficult to prepare positively charged charcoal. The negative and iso-electric charcoals show a strong adsorption of anions.

2. The absorbed layer of electrolytes on the charcoal surface cannot alone be removed by long continued washing and it is necessary to activate the charcoal to remove them.

3. Hydrochloric acid is difficult to remove. If the charcoal has been purified by activation the charge is affected by hydrochloric acid only to a small extent.

We take this opportunity of expressing our thanks to Professor J. N. Mukherjee for suggesting this work and for facilities.

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Received April 6, 1936.
